

CHARACTERISTICS OF TAXATION OF TOURISM SUBJECTS PROVIDING HOTEL SERVICES AS AN EXAMPLE OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *In this article, the experience, practical results and shortcomings of the development of the hospitality industry, which is an important part of the service sector in Uzbekistan, and its development through the laws and tax system developed by the state, are given. As a result of research and analysis, the author made a proposal and response.*

Keywords: *tourism industry, hospitality, tax benefits, number of tourists, investment, standard of living of the population.*

INTRODUCTION

Everyone knows that economic development is the most important issue of countries. The goal of development is the well-being of the population. When a certain country goes through the processes of achieving stable economic indicators using its internal resources, it opens the way for the free operation of the most important sectors that have the ability to bring funds. In particular, the tourism sector and the related hospitality industry at the same time have become an important economic profit-making sector in many countries of the world. The role of the state is high in the development of hotel services and creation of an environment of pure competition in this field. Mainly, it is possible to influence private entrepreneurship through taxation and thus turn the tourism market into a profitable sector. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, systematic and well-defined work on the development of the tourism sector has been consistently continued in recent years.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

After the establishment of tourism as one of the strategic sectors of the national economy by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 2, 2016, consistent work has been done to develop the tourism sector.

As a result of the ongoing reforms, the number of tourists in tourism is significantly increasing compared to previous years. In 2016, the number of tourists who visited the country was 2.02 million, and according to the data of 2023, this figure was 6.6 million.

At the same time, due to the increase in the number of tourists coming to the country, the demand for accommodation facilities has also increased. This was a reason for private entrepreneurs to invest in the tourism industry. According to the results of the analysis, the amount of demand compared to supply in the tourism market of the country increased sharply from year to year. The country is able to show its domestic tourism potential to other countries due to the establishment of promising projects and the establishment of good relations with neighboring countries.

In particular, during this period, the number of foreign visitors increased from 32.7% to 2 times, and the number of rooms in accommodation facilities increased to 29.3% in 2019. (2 photos)

Based on these data, it is effective to attract foreign investments to the development of the country's tourism.

Indicators of growth in the number of foreign tourists, accommodation facilities and their rooms

In addition to increasing the number of means of placement and attracting investments in the expansion of this activity, the taxation system also plays an important role. Based on this, let's consider the taxation system.

According to the new Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on December 30, 2019, depending on the legal form and income of the entities of the tourism sector, in addition to the generally prescribed taxes, types of taxes such as profit tax, turnover tax, income tax, pays tax at the specified rate.

Taxes and their rates imposed on investment vehicles operating as a legal entity

Type of accommodation	Amount of income	Profit tax/turnover tax	Property tax	Land tax	VAT	Personal tax
Hotel	When the income 1 billion soums	15%	2%	Tax arising from the property of land area	15%	12%
Hostel		4% turnover tax				
Others of accommodation	When the income 1 billion soums					

The tax system is a useful guide for the systematic operation of every hotel, but not every businessman understands it. The types of taxes used step by step in the development of the service sector in Uzbekistan support the activities of newly established hotels.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

So, if we consider the above information, the demand for hotel services is high. Only in this case, it is appropriate for us to fully understand the tax incentives created by the state, to use materials that do not harm the environment, and to organize work efficiently by installing energy-

saving devices. Attracting foreign investments is also effective in private business. Compared to large-scale hotels, the demand for hostels, home hotels and camping is currently high. Accordingly, in order to reduce the probability of "risk" in our work, we must start with smaller activities.

In order to encourage investment in the manufacturing industry, decision-makers and the government should develop and implement decisions that will reduce the amount of taxes on factories and products used in the industry to an acceptable level.

Reducing the amount of tax collected from the sales department in hotels can be one of the benefits. Tax regulation puts an end to hidden activities, and this also has its positive effect.

According to the Law "On Foreign Investments", foreign investors in the Republic of Uzbekistan can be:

- Foreign countries, administrative or territorial bodies of foreign countries;
- International organizations established in accordance with interstate agreements or other agreements;
- Any other companies, organizations or associations of legal entities established and operating in accordance with the laws of foreign countries;
- Individuals who are citizens of a foreign country.

The number of hotels operating in the republic, especially home hotels, has increased sharply in recent years. This is the result of agreements and agreements concluded with foreign countries on the development of tourism. We are witnessing the growth of private entrepreneurship by reducing the state participation in tourism. Therefore, based on this, it can be said that it is very necessary to create an environment of pure competition in the free market economy.

1 figure

2 figure

Directions of state participation in the development of the tourism industry (Figs. 1, 2)

In order to control demand and effectively organize activities in tourism, the state influences the supply and demand process in a certain direction. If we recognize that the choice of tourists depends on the price, new strategic work should be carried out in the systems such as investment and taxes in the formation of the price.

CONCLUSION

The results of studies show that tourism is a direction capable of influencing important post-industrial economic development, and taking into account the increase in the number of tourists coming to our country in this field, the demand for hotels is high. In order to meet the growing demand for placement tools, it remains an important issue to further expand the free way to private entrepreneurship, reduce state intervention, and influence buyers through price. At the same time, attracting investments and revising the tax system would be effective. It is appropriate to apply the practice of tax exemptions and tax exemptions for enterprises operating in accordance with the laws of sustainable economy.

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